

showed the presence of two C-methyls at δ 1.99 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{Ar}-\text{CH}_3$) and the four protons (A_2B_2) of the paradisubstituted B-ring as the doublets at δ 6.79 (2H, d, 3'-H and 5'-H) and 7.29 (2H, d, 2'-H and 6'-H). The physical and spectral (uv, ir, nmr and ms) characteristics of compound K suggested it to be identical in all respects with those of farrerol⁶, 4',5,7-trihydroxy-6,8-dimethylflavanone.

Compound L was crystallised from MeOH as pale yellow feathery needles, m.p. 255–60°, $C_{20}H_{18}O_8$; ν_{max} –OH in its ir at 3450 cm^{-1} (OH); gave a diacetate with $\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$, which was crystallised from MeOH as feathery needles, $C_{24}H_{22}O_{10}$, m.p. 168–69°, M^+ 470. Preliminary spectral studies indicated that it might belong to a novel class of compounds whose structural investigation is in progress.

The co-occurrence of different groups of triterpenes and phenolics such as coumarin and flavanone in this plant is of biogenetic significance. Besides, a C-methylflavonoid, farrerol is isolated for the first time from the plants of Sterculiaceae.

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Redox Titration with Manganese(IV) using 2-Nitrodiphenylamine as Indicator

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2-NITRODIPHENYLAMINE (NDA) is known to be a versatile and high potential (1.12 V) reversible redox indicator¹ in the titrimetric analysis with Ce^{IV} , Mn^{VII} and V^{V} . The use of NDA in the titrations with Mn^{IV} in sulphuric acid medium is reported in the present communication.

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Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. A 0.1 N standard arsenic(III) solution, and approximately 0.1 N solutions of iron(II), hydroquinone, hexacyanoferrate(II) and antimony(III) were prepared and standardised². A 0.1 N solution of manganese(IV) was prepared and standardised by the procedure of Mandal and Sant³. 0.01 M iodine-monochloride⁴ and 0.1% solution of NDA in acetic acid were also prepared.

General procedure: The prepared reductant solutions 10–25 ml were diluted to 100 ml maintaining appropriate acidity and were treated with NDA (0.2 ml) and finally titrated with a standard 0.1 N manganese(IV) solution till the colour sharply changed from yellow to red.

Satisfactory titrations could also be carried out with a 0.01 N solution of Mn^{IV} provided an indicator correction of 0.01 ml is applied for 0.2 ml of the indicator used.

Results and Discussion

The acidity conditions for the titrations were fairly wide: 1–5 M for iron(II), 1–6 M for hydroquinone, 1–3 M for arsenic(III) and 1–4 M for antimony(III). However, for hexacyanoferrate(II) 2 M acidity should be maintained. The colour change at the end-point was sharp for all the titrations but first appearance of red colour should be taken as the end-point in the case of hydroquinone. The reactions were sufficiently fast and no catalyst was required for iron(II), hexacyanoferrate(II) and hydroquinone. Small amount (1–3 ml) of 0.01 M iodine monochloride was required as catalyst for arsenic(III) and antimony(III) titrations. The accuracy of results were in the following range: 1–2 milliequivalents (meq.) of iron(II) (with a standard deviation of ± 0.01), 0.5–1.7 meq. of hydroquinone (± 0.02), 0.5–1 meq. of hexacyanoferrate(II) (± 0.01), 1–2 meq. of arsenic(III) (± 0.03), and 0.7–2 meq. of antimony(III) (± 0.02). The proposed method is convenient and is applicable even in dilute solutions.

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